

Post Session Questionnaire

What was your overall satisfaction with the *<complete with probe name>* you interacted with? Mark your level of satisfaction

Given the following adjectives, how would you describe the *<complete with probe name>*?
Circle as many options you find appropriate

Pros
Accessible
Consistent
Desirable
Empowering
Fast
Helpful
Intuitive
Motivating
Novel
Relevant
Stimulating
Valuable

Cons
Annoying
Boring
Confusing
Dull
Frustrating
Hard to use
Ineffective
Old
Poor quality
Rigid
Stressful
Unattractive

For the research team to fill - ID: _____

Did anything catch your attention in any way while using the *<complete with probe name>*?

Would you like to change anything regarding the *<complete with probe name>*?

Feel free to write anything else you did not have the opportunity to expose regarding the *<complete with probe name>* or the study in other questions!

For the research team to fill - ID: _____